

ANZLEAD Work Package 3.1: Technical Report

ANZLEAD Data darmonisation tools and harmonised data

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ADA Metadata Management _____	3
Process steps for uploading vocabularies _____	3
1.1 Download the tabular data _____	3
1.2 Processing of the basket csv for PoolParty _____	5
1.3 Uploading the csv to PoolParty _____	6
Australian Election Study: An ANZLEAD harmonisation project _____	8
AES Cumulative data _____	8
Harmonisation code _____	9

Metadata creation and Research Vocabularies

1. ADA Metadata Management

ADA has implemented the metadata management and documentation platform, Colectica, to provide a registry service for use in archivist data processing. Functionality includes both internal reuse and interoperability for data archivists, but also potential reuse for findability and reusability in dissemination.

Colectica is a centralized system for managing data resources, enabling collaborative workflows, and providing automatic version control. ADA uses Colectica to manage, search, and re-use category and code lists across multiple surveys and datasets. In the current workflow, metadata collections are published to a server where that metadata can be structured and shared online. Across a collection of demonstrator projects, the ADA has produced crosswalk tables of response codes and labels across multiple waves of data to facilitate harmonisation of this data. The first stage of this process has produced harmonised cumulative datasets of questions and response categories that are common across multiple waves of data and can now be easily accessed and analysed by researchers.

ADA has developed an internal process to partially automate the extraction of codelists from Colectica Portal and preparation of these metadata for upload to ARDC Research Vocabularies Australia (RVA). As detailed below, sections of metadata can be selected and downloaded in .csv format. A python script is run to format the .csv data for compatibility with the RVA data editor, PoolParty.

1.1. Process steps for uploading vocabularies

This section explains how to download the data from the ADA metadata repository (Colectica) and then upload them to the Research Vocabularies Australia (RVA) editor, PoolParty.

1.1.1 Download the tabular data

Step 1: create a new basket in your account and go to the survey of interest.

Figure 1

MDR Staging Search Explore Help Baskets 0

- Administrative
- Ageing
- Australia and the World
- Citizenship**
 - Children
 - Democracy
 - Parents
 - Political Protest
 - Rights and privileges
- Community Life
- Consumption
- Crime and justice
- Culture and society
- Demographics and population
- Describing Australia
- Economic policy
- Economics
- Education
- Environment
- Families and Relationships
- Geographic
- Government policy and services

View: Concordance

Concordance: Wide

Item Name	Australian Survey of Social Attitudes 2003	ausa_2003_data	Australian Survey of Social Attitudes 2003
Good citizen: Always vote in elections			V48
Good citizen: Never try to evade taxes			V48
Good citizen: Always obey laws			V50
Good citizen: Keep watch on government			V51
Good citizen: Active in associations			V52
Good citizen: Understand other opinions			V53

Step 2: select the vocabularies using the shopping carts (see Figure 1)

Step 3: Go to your basket and click download metadata, and select csv as the option (see Figure 2).

Figure 2

Variables (69)

Download Metadata ▾	
PDF Codebook	MODE Mode of survey completion AUSSI-ESS > AuSSI-ESS 2020 Published > AuSSI-ESS_2020_Published
CSV	
Excel	SEX SEX. What sex are you? AUSSI-ESS > AuSSI-ESS 2020 Published > AuSSI-ESS_2020_Published
DDI 3.2 XML	
PPLTRST	A4. Generally speaking, would you say that most people can be trusted, or that you can't be too careful in dealing with people? AUSSI-ESS > AuSSI-ESS 2020 Published > AuSSI-ESS_2020_Published
NETUSTM	A3. On a typical day, about how much time do you spend using the internet on a computer, tablet, smartphone or other device, whether for work or personal use? (in minutes) AUSSI-ESS > AuSSI-ESS 2020 Published > AuSSI-ESS_2020_Published
NETUSOFT	A2. People can use the internet on different devices such as computers, tablets and smartphones. How often do you use the internet on these or any other devices, whether for work or personal use? AUSSI-ESS > AuSSI-ESS 2020 Published > AuSSI-ESS_2020_Published
NWSPOL	A1. On a typical day, about how much time do you spend watching, reading, or listening to news about politics and current affairs? (in minutes) AUSSI-ESS > AuSSI-ESS 2020 Published > AuSSI-ESS_2020_Published

The csv file will look something like Fig 3.

Figure 3

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M
1	Name Label Type Codes Description Study Dataset												
2	MODE "Mode of survey completion" Code "1"	Online 2	Phone	"AuSSI-ESS 2020 Published"	AuSSI-ESS_2020_Published								
3	SEX "SEX. What sex are you?" Code "1"	Male 2	Female 3	Refused 4	Don't know	"AuSSI-ESS 2020 Published"	AuSSI-ESS_2020_Published						
4	PPLTRST "A4. Generally speaking	would you say that most people can be trusted or that you can't	0 - You can't be 3	2 4	3 5	4 6	5 7	6 8	7 9	8 10	9 11		
5	NETUSTM "A3. On a typical day	about how much time do you spend using the	tablet	smartphone or o whether for work 2	9 3	10 4	15 5	20 6	30 7	38 8	40 9		
6	NETUSOFT "A2. People can use the internet on different device	tablets and smartphones. How often do you us whether for work	Never 2	Only occasional A few times a wk	Most days 5	Every day 6	Refused 7	Don't know	"AuSSI-ESS 2020 Published"	AuSSI-ESS_2020_P			
7	NWSPOL "A1. On a typical day	about how much time do you spend watching	reading	or listening to ne 2	1 3	2 4	3 5	5 6	7 7	10 8	15 9	20 10	
8	POLINTR "B1. How interested would you say you are in politics	Very interested 2	Quite interested	Hardly interested	Not at all interest	Refused 6	Don't know	"AuSSI-ESS 2020 Published"	AuSSI-ESS_2020_Published				
9	PSPPSGOVA "B2. How much would you say the political system	Not at all 2	Very little 3	Some 4	A lot 5	A great deal 6	Refused 7	Don't know	"AuSSI-ESS 2020 Published"	AuSSI-ESS_2020_Published			
10	HMSACLD "B36. Agree or disagree - Gay male and lesbian cox	Agree strongly 2	Agree 3	Neither agree nc	Disagree 5	Disagree strongl	Refused 7	Don't know	"AuSSI-ESS 2020 Published"	AuSSI-ESS_2020_Published			
11	CTZSHIPC "C21. What citizenship do you hold?" Code "14	Australia 48	China 56	Don't know 77	United Kingdom	Indonesia 105	India 158	Malaysia 171	New Zealand 1	Pakistan 189	Refused 888	Others	"AuSSI-ESS 2020 P
12	BRNCNTR "C22. Were you born in Australia?" Code "1"	Yes 2	No 3	Refused 4	Don't know	"AuSSI-ESS 2020 Published"	AuSSI-ESS_2020_Published						
13	EDULVLFP "F44. What is the highest level of education your h	wife	or partner has s	Less than Grade	Year 6 Year 10 to Year	Certificate I or II	Year 12 6	Certificate III 7	Certificate IV 8	Associate Degree	Diploma or Advi	Bachelor's I	
14	P_GENDER "What is your gender?" Code "1"	Refused 2	Don't know 3	Not stated / Unk	Male 5	Female 6	Other	"AuSSI-ESS 2020 Published"	AuSSI-ESS_2020_Published				
15	P_AGE "Age as of 29th February 2020" Code "1"	Unknown 2	18 3	19 4	20 5	21 6	22 7	23 8	24 9	25 10	26 11	27 12	28 13
16	P_AGE_GROUP "Age group as of 29th February 2020" Code "	Unknown 2	18-24 years 3	25-34 years 4	35-44 years 5	45-54 years 6	55-64 years 7	65-74 years 8	75 or more years	"AuSSI-ESS 2020 Published"	AuSSI-ESS_2020_Published		
17	D_COB_GROUP "Respondent country of birth grouping - deriv	Refused 2	Don't know 3	Not stated / Unk	Australian born Mainly NESB	ba Mainly ESB background	"AuSSI-ESS 2020 Published"	AuSSI-ESS_2020_Published					
18	P_CITIZEN "Are you an Australian citizen?" Code "1"	Refused 2	Don't know 3	Yes 4	No	"AuSSI-ESS 2020 Published"	AuSSI-ESS_2020_Published						
19	D_EDUCATION "Highest educational qualification - derived" Cc	Not stated / Unknown 2	Postgraduate Dc	Graduate Dc	Bachelor Degree	Advanced Diplo	Certificate III & I	Secondary Educ	Secondary Educ	Certificate I & II	Secondary Education - Years 9 and below	"A	
20													

1.1.2 Processing of the basket csv for PoolParty

Windows

This step assumes the user installed Python and Make on their system (install Chocolatey, and then type 'choco install Make' in the terminal). Download the folder that corresponds to Windows.

step 1: go into the directory of your choice that contains the basket csv file and the python script Scrapper.py and Makefile.

step 2: open a terminal from the directory and run:

```
make
```

step 3: run

```
.\myenv\Scripts\python.exe Scrapper.py Name/of/your/basket/csv/file
```

Linux/Mac

This step assumes the user installed Python and Make on their system. Download the folder that corresponds to Linux/Mac.

step 1: go into the directory of your choice that contains the basket csv file and the python script Scrapper.py and Makefile.

step 2: open a terminal from the directory and run:

```
make
```

step 3: run

```
python Scrapper.py Name/of/your/basket/csv/file
```

The output file (output.csv) will look something like Figure 4 and it is now ready for PoolParty upload.

1.1.3 Uploading the csv to PoolParty

Following the instructions on how to upload to PoolParty on the PoolParty website (<https://documentation.ardc.edu.au/rva/importing-a-vocabulary-to-poolparty-spreadsheet-cs>), we can now import the output.csv into PoolParty (see figure 5).

Figure 5

2. Australian Election Study: An ANZLEAD harmonisation project

The Australian Election Study (AES) is a longitudinal study of political attitudes and behaviour in Australia. The study has surveyed Australian voters since 1987, providing an important resource for understanding historic trends in voter demographics and attitudes about politics and social issues in Australia. The AES provides insights election outcomes as well as public opinion on a range of key policy issues.

AES reports are currently available for Australian federal elections from 1987 to 2022 at <https://australianelectionstudy.org/>

AES data from all 13 waves of the Voter Study is available for download from the Australian Data Archive at <https://dataverse.ada.edu.au/dataverse/australian-voter-study>

2.1 AES Cumulative data

As part of the ANZLEAD project, the ADA has created a harmonised version of the AES data, incorporating all variables that appear in at least two waves of the project into a single cumulative data file. To achieve this, all thirteen data files were ingested using the metadata management software, Colectica. Colectica was then used to reproduce the codelists and value labels for each variable in crosswalk tables comparing those metadata across every wave.

For example, below is a screenshot of metadata for a question about “interest in politics”. All value labels used are displayed in the left-most column, and the coding scheme for each wave of the survey are shown in the remaining columns, chronologically from left to right.

Australian Election Study												
Item Name	Australian Election Study 1987	Australian Election Study 1990	Australian Election Study 1993	Australian Election Study 1996	Australian Election Study 1998	Australian Election Study 2001	Australian Election Study 2004	Australian Election Study 2007	Australian Election Study 2010	Australian Election Study 2013	Australian Election Study 2016	Australian Election Study 2019
	aes87_datafile q14	aes90_datafile a4	aes93_datafile a3	aes96_datafile a1	aes98_datafile A1	aes01_datafile intpol	aes04_datafile a1	aes07_datafile a1	aes10_datafile a1	aes13_datafile a1	aes16_datafile A1	aes19_datafile A1
Blank				-1								
Missing		0			-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1		
NO RESPONSE												
No attention						0						
A good deal	1	1	1	1	1		1	1	1	1	1	1
Some	2	2	2	2	2		2	2	2	2	2	2
Not much	3	3	3	3	3		3	3	3	3	3	3
None at all				4								
None	4	4	4		4		4	4	4	4	4	4
Great deal of attention						10						
Don't know						11						
Item skipped											999	99

The crosswalk tables are copied to an Excel workbook, where an archivist recodes responses to minimise the variation in response categories as much as possible and ensure that response categories are coded consistently across all waves (i.e., the metadata is harmonised).

Source to Target mapping												
Mapped by user												
Target name	polintr	aes87_datafi	aes90_datafi	aes93_datafi	aes96_datafi	aes98_datafi	aes01_datafi	aes04_datafi	aes07_datafi	aes10_datafi	aes13_datafi	aes16_datafi
Target category	Label	q14	a4	a3	a1							
Not asked	-9							-9				
Changed response format	-8											
Blank	-4				-1							
No response	-3	0										
Skipped	-2											999
Missing	-1		0			-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	
A good deal	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Some	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Not much	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
None at all	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Dont know	5											

2.2 Harmonisation code

With the workbook and original data files organised in an appropriate directory structure, an R script developed by the ADA team is executed to generate and run an SPSS syntax that (a) creates copies of each original AES data file, (b) applies all re-labelling and re-coding specified in the workbook to each affected variable in the new datafiles, (c) remove any variables that are not to be harmonised, and (d) saves the now-harmonised data files.

The AES harmonisation script is available from Github:

https://github.com/ADA-ANU/ADA_Research_Data_Tools/tree/main/AES%20harmonising

A second SPSS syntax has been prepared to merge the harmonised data files into a single cumulative file. This code builds the cumulative file by merging datafiles one by one, matching variables to any existing variables by name. A dummy variable is also generated to identify responses by their wave. The final section of the code computes an AES_wave variable from these dummy wave indicators.

```

DATASET ACTIVATE aes87_datafile.
COMPUTE AES_wave=1.
IF (aes1990 = 1) AES_wave=2.
IF (aes1993 = 1) AES_wave=3.
IF (aes1996 = 1) AES_wave=4.
IF (aes1998 = 1) AES_wave=5.
IF (aes2001 = 1) AES_wave=6.
IF (aes2004 = 1) AES_wave=7.
IF (aes2007 = 1) AES_wave=8.
IF (aes2010 = 1) AES_wave=9.
IF (aes2013 = 1) AES_wave=10.
IF (aes2016 = 1) AES_wave=11.
IF (aes2019 = 1) AES_wave=12.
IF (aes2022 = 1) AES_wave=13.
EXECUTE.
VARIABLE LABELS AES_wave
'AES wave'.
ADD VALUE LABELS AES_wave
1 'AES1987'
2 'AES1990'
3 'AES1993'
4 'AES1996'
5 'AES1998'
6 'AES2001'
7 'AES2004'
8 'AES2007'
9 'AES2010'
10 'AES2013'
11 'AES2016'
12 'AES2019'
13 'AES2022'.
EXECUTE.

```

The cumulative data file is available as part of the AES collection on ADA Dataverse. The file will be updated with each subsequent wave of AES data using the established harmonisation process detailed here.

The final release of the AES Cumulative file is available from the Australian Data Archive at:
<http://dx.doi.org/10.26193/HJ3KT1>